

Interactive Oral Communication Activities as a Means to Develop Self-sufficiency of Grade 11 Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the effectiveness of interactive oral communication activities in developing self-sufficiency among Grade 11 students. Specifically, it examined students' confidence, fluency, vocabulary, engagement, and independence, as well as the difficulties they encountered. The study utilized a descriptive research design with 45 Grade 11 HUMSS students from Alangilan Senior High School as respondents. A validated researcher-made questionnaire was used to collect data, which were analyzed using frequency, percentage, ranking, weighted mean, and composite mean.

The results revealed that students strongly agreed that interactive oral communication activities positively impact their communication skills (3.65). The activities improved students' confidence (3.38), fluency (3.33), and vocabulary (3.22). Moreover, students showed high engagement (3.50) and improved independence (3.40). However, fear of making mistakes and being judged remained a major difficulty (3.39).

The study concludes that interactive oral communication activities are effective in developing students' self-sufficiency, although supportive classroom environments are necessary to reduce anxiety. It is recommended that teachers integrate more interactive activities and create a safe learning space to enhance students' communication skills.

Keywords: *oral communication, self-sufficiency, student engagement, fluency, confidence*

1. Introduction

Background and Rationale

Effective communication is one of the most essential skills needed for success in both academic and real-life situations. In today's globalized and interconnected world, students are expected to communicate confidently and independently, particularly in the English language. However, many learners still struggle with oral communication due to limited vocabulary, lack of confidence, fear of making mistakes, and insufficient opportunities for active participation.

Self-sufficiency in communication refers to a learner's ability to express ideas clearly, confidently, and independently in different situations. Developing this skill is crucial in preparing students for the demands of the 21st century. One effective way to enhance this is through the integration of interactive oral communication activities such as role-playing, debates, storytelling, and group discussions. These activities provide authentic opportunities for students to engage in meaningful communication and improve their speaking abilities.

Despite the emphasis of the Department of Education on strengthening communication skills through curriculum reforms, many students continue to experience difficulties in expressing themselves orally. This situation highlights the need to explore teaching strategies that can enhance students' confidence, fluency, and independence in communication. Thus, this study focuses on the integration of interactive oral communication activities as a means to develop self-sufficiency among Grade 11 students.

Review of Related Literature

Several studies support the effectiveness of interactive oral communication activities in improving students' speaking skills. Interactive approaches, such as Communicative Language Teaching, allow learners to engage in real-life conversations, enhancing their ability to express ideas and interact with others effectively.

According to Omar et al. (2020), interactive language learning activities create a positive learning environment that motivates students to participate and improve their speaking skills. Similarly, Hue (2024) found that communicative activities significantly enhance students' confidence and willingness to engage in speaking tasks.

In addition, Briones (2022) emphasized that interactive learning activities help develop students' self-confidence gradually through active participation. De Leon and Olegario (2024) also highlighted that collaborative learning improves students' speaking competence and creates a less threatening learning environment.

In terms of fluency, studies show that speaking activities such as role-playing and group discussions help learners practice real-life communication, thereby improving their ability to

speak naturally and continuously. Vocabulary development is also enhanced through interactive methods, as learners are exposed to meaningful language use rather than memorization alone.

However, despite these benefits, several studies identified challenges in oral communication. Chand (2021) and Sevela (2019) reported that students often experience anxiety, fear of judgment, and lack of confidence when speaking in English. These challenges indicate the need for supportive classroom environments and effective teaching strategies to help learners overcome communication barriers.

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the effectiveness of interactive oral communication activities in developing self-sufficiency among Grade 11 students in Alangilan Senior High School.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What are the distinct features of interactive oral communication activities in English?
2. How do interactive oral communication activities develop self-sufficiency in terms of:
 - confidence in speaking
 - fluency
 - vocabulary and language use?
3. To what extent are these activities integrated in terms of:
 - level of engagement
 - level of independency?
4. What difficulties do students encounter in performing interactive oral communication activities?
5. What interactive oral communication activities may be proposed to further develop self-sufficiency?

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to develop self-sufficiency among Grade 11 students through interactive oral communication activities.

2. Materials and Methods

Research Design

This study employed a **descriptive research design** to determine the effectiveness of integrating interactive oral communication activities in developing self-sufficiency among Grade

11 students. Descriptive research is appropriate for this study as it focuses on describing the characteristics, perceptions, and experiences of the respondents regarding the use of interactive oral communication activities.

Subjects of the Study

The participants of the study were **forty-five (45) Grade 11 HUMSS students** from Alangilan Senior High School during the First Semester of School Year 2025–2026.

The respondents were selected using a **complete enumeration**, as all students in one section handled by the researcher were included in the study. This ensured that all relevant data from the group were collected.

Data Gathering Instruments

The study utilized a **researcher-made questionnaire** as the primary data-gathering instrument. The questionnaire was designed based on related literature and studies and underwent validation by experts, including the school principal and master teachers.

The instrument consisted of four parts:

1. Distinct features of interactive oral communication activities
2. Self-sufficiency (confidence, fluency, vocabulary and language use)
3. Level of engagement and independency
4. Difficulties encountered in oral communication activities

A **Likert scale** was used to measure responses, with corresponding interpretations ranging from strongly agree to disagree.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher first secured permission from the school principal to conduct the study. Consent from the respondents was also obtained prior to data collection.

After approval, the validated questionnaire was distributed to the participants in printed form. The respondents were given sufficient time to answer the questionnaire.

Once completed, the questionnaires were retrieved, checked for completeness, and organized for data analysis. The responses were then tallied and submitted to a statistician for proper statistical treatment.

Data Analysis Plan

The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools, including:

- **Frequency and Percentage** – to determine the number and proportion of responses
- **Ranking** – to identify the order of responses based on importance
- **Weighted Mean** – to measure the average responses of the participants
- **Composite Mean** – to determine the overall average of responses

These statistical tools were used to interpret the data and answer the research questions effectively.

3. Results

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data gathered from the respondents. The results are organized according to the research questions and are supported by descriptive statistical measures such as weighted mean and composite mean.

Distinct Features of Interactive Oral Communication Activities

Table 1
Distinct Features of Interactive Oral Communication Activities

<i>Interactive Oral Communication Activities...</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. help me gain confidence when speaking in English	3.67	Strongly Agree	4
2. encourage me to participate in class discussions	3.56	Strongly Agree	7
3. make my learning more engaging and fun	3.73	Strongly Agree	2
4. integrate technology-enhanced learning tools and make our class interactive	3.47	Agree	8
5. promote teamwork and collaboration	3.60	Strongly Agree	6
6. enhance my vocabulary and communication skills	3.71	Strongly Agree	3
7. improve fluency and ability to speak spontaneously	3.64	Strongly Agree	5
8. offer relevant topics and activities that can improve my communication skills	3.78	Strongly Agree	1
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.65	Strongly Agree	

As shown in the table the results revealed that students strongly agreed on the positive features of interactive oral communication activities, with an overall composite mean of 3.65. The highest-rated indicator was “offer relevant topics and activities that can improve communication skills” (WM = 3.78), followed by “make learning more engaging and fun” (WM = 3.73). Meanwhile, “integration of technology-enhanced tools” received the lowest rating (WM = 3.47), although still interpreted as “Agree.” These findings indicate that students highly value meaningful, engaging, and skill-oriented communication activities.

Table 2

**Integration of Interactive Oral Communication Activities to
 Develop Self-sufficiency – Confidence in Speaking**

Confidence in Speaking <i>Because of the interactive oral communication activities...</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I feel more confident to speak in front of others	3.47	Agree	2
2. I can express my ideas clearly and coherently	3.29	Agree	3
3. I am more willing to start and participate in conversations	3.62	Strongly Agree	1
4. I can overcome my anxiety in speaking English	3.24	Agree	4
5. I am less afraid of making mistakes when I speak in class	3.27	Agree	5
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.38	Agree	

Table 2 presents the result of the integration of interactive oral communication activities to develop self-sufficiency in terms of confidence in speaking.

Results show that students agreed that interactive activities improved their confidence, with a composite mean of 3.38. The highest-rated item was “willingness to start and participate in conversations” (WM = 3.62), indicating increased participation. However, “being less afraid of making mistakes” received the lowest mean (WM = 3.27), suggesting that anxiety is still present among some learners.

Table 3

**Integration of Interactive Oral Communication Activities to
 Develop Self-sufficiency – Fluency**

Fluency <i>Because of the interactive oral communication activities...</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can use appropriate words and expressions naturally	3.33	Agree	2
2. I can organize my thoughts efficiently when speaking	3.31	Agree	3
3. I can now speak in English during class discussions and conversations	3.49	Agree	1
4. I am able to lessen my mistakes and repetition of words during conversation	3.29	Agree	4
5. I am able to speak longer without losing my train of thoughts	3.22	Agree	5
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.33	Agree	

Table 3 shows the result of the integration of interactive oral communication activities to develop self-sufficiency in terms of fluency in speaking. The findings indicate that students agreed that their fluency improved, with a composite mean of 3.33.

The highest-rated item was “ability to speak in English during discussions” (WM = 3.49). On the other hand, “ability to speak longer without losing train of thought” ranked lowest (WM = 3.22), indicating that extended speaking remains a challenge.

Table 4
Integration of Interactive Oral Communication Activities to
Develop Self-sufficiency – Vocabulary and Language Use

Vocabulary and Language Use <i>Because of the interactive oral communication activities...</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can investigate and explore new words	3.49	Agree	2.5
2. I can use variety of words	3.40	Agree	4
3. I can choose accurate words and construct meaningful sentences	3.49	Agree	2.5
4. I am more aware of my grammar when engaging in conversations and classroom discussions	3.51	Agree	1
5. I lessen my grammar mistakes when participating in speaking activities	3.20	Strongly Agree	5
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.22	Agree	

Table 4 shows the result of the integration of interactive oral communication activities to develop self-sufficiency in terms of vocabulary and language use. Students also agreed that their vocabulary and language use improved, with a composite mean of 3.22.

The highest-ranked indicator was “awareness of grammar during communication” (WM = 3.51). The lowest-ranked indicator was “lessening grammar mistakes” (WM = 3.20), although still positively rated.

Table 5
Extent of the Integration of Interactive Oral communication
Activities – Level of Engagement

Level of Engagement	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I feel more engage during classroom discussion because of the interactive oral communication activities	3.58	Strongly Agree	1
2. I actively involve myself in group discussions and presentation	3.53	Strongly Agree	2.5
3. I am more likely to volunteer in class when there are interactive oral communication tasks	3.33	Agree	5
4. I feel more interested and motivated to speak in class	3.51	Strongly Agree	4
5. I look forward joining for more interactive oral communication activities	3.53	Strongly Agree	2.5
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.50	Strongly Agree	

Table 5 illustrates the extent of the integration of oral communication activities among students relative to level of engagement. Students strongly agreed that interactive activities increased their engagement, with a composite mean of 3.50. The highest-rated statement was “feeling more engaged during classroom discussions” (WM = 3.58). The lowest was “volunteering in class” (WM = 3.33), suggesting that some hesitation still exists.

Table 6
Extent of the Integration of Interactive Oral communication
Activities – Level of Independency

Level of Independency	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can identify my strengths and weaknesses in speaking English	3.49	Agree	2
2. I can express my ideas without relying much to the teacher	3.20	Agree	5
3. I can work and contribute effectively to the class even without constant supervision	3.22	Agree	4
4. I decide for myself how to present or respond during speaking activities	3.38	Agree	3
5. I find ways to improve and enhance my communication skills	3.71	Strongly Agree	1
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.40	Agree	

Table 6, shows the extent of the integration of oral communication activities among students relative to level of independency. Results show that students agreed that their independency improved, with a composite mean of 3.40. The highest-rated item was “finding ways to improve communication skills” (WM = 3.71), indicating strong initiative. The lowest was “expressing ideas without relying on the teacher” (WM = 3.20), showing partial dependence on guidance.

Table 7
Difficulties encountered in performing the different interactive oral
communication activities

Difficulties encountered by the students...	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I find it challenging to perform in front of my classmates	3.64	Strongly Agree	2
2. I sometimes have trouble in pronunciation and use of correct grammar	3.40	Agree	4
3. I find it hard to express my ideas clearly in English	3.42	Agree	3
4. I am afraid of making mistakes and being judged by others	3.76	Strongly Agree	1
5. I sometimes feel lazy and reluctant in performing interactive oral communication activities, especially when I am not motivated and interested in the activity.	3.24	Agree	5
6. I struggle in analyzing and understanding the instructions of my classmates and teachers during oral communication tasks	3.16	Agree	6
7. I sometimes feel anxious and nervous when I need to speak in English.	3.11	Agree	7
COMPOSITE MEAN	3.39	Agree	

Table 7 shows the difficulties encountered by the students in performing oral communication activities. Students agreed on the presence of difficulties, with a composite mean of 3.39. The most significant difficulty was “fear of making mistakes and being judged” (WM = 3.76), followed by “difficulty performing in front of classmates” (WM = 3.64). The least reported difficulty was “feeling anxious when speaking English” (WM = 3.11), though still present.

4. Discussion

The findings of the study indicate that interactive oral communication activities are effective in enhancing students’ communication skills and self-sufficiency. The improvement in confidence, fluency, and vocabulary suggests that students benefit from active participation in meaningful speaking tasks. These findings support previous studies which emphasize that interactive and student-centered approaches promote better communication skills.

The high level of engagement indicates that interactive activities create a more dynamic and motivating learning environment. Students become more involved in discussions and are encouraged to participate actively. Similarly, the development of independence shows that students are able to take initiative in improving their communication skills.

However, the presence of fear and anxiety among students highlights the need for a supportive and non-threatening classroom environment. Fear of being judged remains a significant barrier to participation. Teachers should therefore create a safe space where students feel comfortable expressing their ideas without fear of criticism.

Additionally, while improvements were observed, some students still struggle with fluency and grammar. This suggests that continuous practice and exposure to interactive activities are necessary for further development.

Overall, the integration of interactive oral communication activities is an effective strategy in improving students’ self-sufficiency, but it should be supported by proper guidance and a positive learning environment.

5. Conclusion

The study concludes that interactive oral communication activities significantly improve the self-sufficiency of Grade 11 students in terms of confidence, fluency, vocabulary, engagement, and independence. These activities encourage active participation and help students develop essential communication skills.

However, students still experience fear of making mistakes, which affects their performance. Therefore, teachers should create a supportive and encouraging classroom environment.

Recommendations

- Teachers should integrate varied interactive activities in lessons.
- Schools should provide training and workshops on communication strategies.
- A supportive classroom environment must be maintained.
- Future studies may explore other strategies to enhance oral communication skills.

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